

A Unique Case of a Pleural Hemangioma Presenting as Recurrent Pleural Effusion

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ABSTRACT

Hemangioma is a benign vascular proliferation which usually occurs in a pediatric skin and regresses with age. It can also occur in unusual location like liver, muscle, brain and lungs. Smaller hemangiomas can be asymptomatic and found incidentally unlike larger hemangioma which can present as pressure symptoms. We present a rare case of a pleural hemangioma presenting as recurrent pleural effusion.

Keywords: Hemangioma; pleural effusion; Interventional radiology-guided lung biopsy

INTRODUCTION

Hemangioma is a benign vascular tumour caused by the abnormal proliferation of vascular endothelial cells. Underlying pathogenesis includes an imbalance between proangiogenic factors and angiogenesis inhibitors. Mostly, infants get cutaneous hemangiomas which regress with age. But they can also appear on internal organs like the liver (most common), lungs, brain, heart and very rarely in the pleura. They are usually asymptomatic but are known to rupture and bleed with pressure. We report a unique case of pleural hemangioma in an elderly female who presented with recurrent pleural effusion.

CASE SUMMARY

An 84-year-old caucasian female with established hypertension, hyperlipidemia, seasonal allergies, chronic sinusitis, glaucoma and recurrent right pleural effusion presented to the emergency room with shortness of breath and coughs ongoing for 2 days. On examination, there were absent lung sounds on the right chest compared to the left side. The rest of the cardiovascular and abdominal examinations were normal. Chest radiography detected a large right pleural effusion with consolidation and mediastinal shift. The patient underwent pigtail catheter placement which continued to drain about 400-200 cc a day. pleural fluid was clear, red cell count <2000; total nucleated cell count of 94; exudative but cytology was negative for malignancy. Gram stain; culture and acid-fast stain of the pleural fluid were negative. Computed tomography of the chest revealed lung mass right posterior medial chest wall involving the pleural space and spinous musculature with cortical destruction of the right 10th rib (Figure 1). Interventional radiology-guided lung biopsy demonstrated numerous blood vessels of capillary size lined by slightly enlarged endothelial cells and the lumen is filled with blood (Figure 2). There is no evidence of atypia, mitotic figures or necrosis noted within this capillary proliferation. The vascular proliferation is positive for CD34 and negative for pankeratin, TTF-1 and D2-40 immunostains. Ki 67 immunostain reveals no significant proliferative activity (<1%). This confirmed a diagnosis of Pleural hemangioma. Echocardiography showed an ejection fraction of 62%. The patient was referred to higher tertiary care centre for surgical intervention.

Figure 1: Computed tomography of the chest arrow demonstrates a lung mass arising from the right posterior medial chest wall and extends to the spinous musculature

Figure 2: Lung biopsy: Tuft of capillary size blood vessels lined by endothelial cells in the vascular lumen

DISCUSSION

Hemangioma is a benign vascular neoplasm that usually affects the infantile skin but can be found in all the organs^[1]. They can be classified as capillary, strawberry, or cavernous hemangiomas based on the vessel size- smallest diameter being the Capillary hemangiomas whereas cavernous hemangiomas consisting of larger diameter. Capillary hemangioma usually involves the skin whereas cavernous hemangioma involves deeper tissues like the skull^[2].

Rarely, hemangioma originates from any part of the chest wall like the rib, intercostal muscles or pleura similar to posterior chest wall lesion in our patient. Very few cases of pleural hemangioma have been reported till date. It can be congenital (Von-Hippel Lindau disease), idiopathic like our patient or acquired mostly through trauma^[3,4].

Usually, hemangiomas are asymptomatic and discovered incidentally on imaging but rarely, they present with symptoms based on the structure they invade. In our female, hemorrhagic pleural effusion was induced by spontaneous rupture of the large hemangioma likely by respiratory movements. Asymptomatic hemangiomas can be monitored closely without any intervention. Larger and symptomatic lesions can be managed conservatively with dry ice cryotherapy, radiotherapy, steroid treatment, sclerosing agent injection, vascular ligation, vascular embolism or surgical excision^[5].

To summarize, pleural hemangioma should be considered as one of the differentials for any patient presenting with recurrent hemorrhagic pleural effusion. Histopathology plays an important role in diagnosis. Our case will join the group of a handful of cases reported in the world.

Disclosure and Conflict of Interest: None

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